

POLYFURFURYL ALCOHOL THERMOSETS RESINS IN FIRE RESISTANT COMPOSITE APPLICATIONS

SUMMARY RESULTS OF THE FIRERESIST PROJECT

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Keywords: Polyfurfuryl alcohol (PFA), Fire resistant composites, Renewable biosourced matrix

In several EU funded projects (BIOCOMP, NATEX, BIOBUILD and FIRERESIST) a new class of renewable liquid polyfurfuryl alcohol resins have synthesized and developed for composite applications. High stiffness, compatibility with natural and mineral fibres as inherent fire resistance are key characteristics of these polymerized materials. The presentation will feature results coming from FIRERESIST project where these resins were investigated for their use in fire proof composite applications.

PFA resins are new in application of fibre reinforced products. The backbone of these VOC-free liquid resins is formed by condensation reactions of furfuryl alcohol. The resulting polymer can be adjusted to specific viscosities by adding water whilst the curing kinetics are adjustable by acid catalysts. The resulting crosslinked polymer is an infusible solid with high Tg and char formation properties at elevated temperatures. Furfuryl alcohol, the monomer, is derived from furfural a renewable chemical which is produced from hemicellulose fraction of agricultural waste in a steam digestion process. Over the last decade Polyfurfuryl alcohol (PFA) resins have seen application in natural fibre composites for the automotive and building industry as well as consumer products. The combination of a functional biomass based resin system and fibre reinforcement forms appealing product-market combinations.

Figure 1: Molecular structure of liquied Polyfurfuryl alcohol resin (PFA)

FIRERESIST-project: Developing Novel Fire-Resistant High Performance Composites :

In FireResist, PFA resins are used as high performance polymer matrix for composite materials in the transport sectors (aerospace, naval and railway applications). A full study and development has been performed to use PFA resins in VA-RTM and Prepreg to applications to produce fire resistant composite materials.

Within this project several aspects of the use PFA resins were investigated in the respective workpackages: a benchmark study on the comparison PFA resins compared to phenolic resin in fibre reinforced products, an investigation of the potential of using colloidal silica as nanoadditive to PFA resins and application of PFA resins in case study demonstrators for public transport.

A summary of the studies along with the most important results are discussed below.

- a) Benchmark study on the comparison PFA resins compared to phenolic resin in fibre reinforced products.

PFA resin systems are characterized by their ability to yield high contents of char upon exposure to high temperatures during fire. Overall project findings indicate that in PFA resins can be used a replacement for know phenolic matrices in fire resistant composite material. With the use of full bath prepreg impregnation of plain weave 300g/m² glass fabric prepreps were manufactured with a 20-25wt% resin content of either phenolic resin or PFA. After consolidation at 140°C during 40 minutes at 20 bars the resulting composites were demoulded and tested for mechanical and thermal properties (table 1 and 2).

Figure 2: Glass-PFA prepreg and compression moulding

Table 1: Comparison of thermal properties of a press moulded Glass-phenolic prepreg vs a Glass ó PFA prepreg in a cone calorimeter test of 50kW/m² at 25mm distance

	1 Glass- Phenolic	2 Glass – PFA
Thickness (mm)	2,70	3,15
Mass (g)	63,80	72,34
Time of ignition (s)	139	125
Time of extinction (s)	325	325
MARHE (kW/m²)	17,51	16,96
Total heat release (MJ/m²)	21,00	19,6
Maximun of heat release (kW/m²)	38,95	44,09

Table 2: Comparison of mechanical properties of a press moulded Glass-phenolic prepreg vs a Glass ó PFA prepreg in 3 point bending at room and elevated temperature.

Material type	Flexural strength (MPa)@25°C	Elastic modulus (GPa)@25°C	Flexural strength (MPa)@90°C	Elastic modulus (MPa) @90°C
Glass - PFA	267	24	208	23
Glass- Phenolic	238	25	208	20

b) Investigation of the potential of using colloidal silica as nanoadditive to PFA resins.

The addition of nano-sized particles to a polymer matrix has led to materials with radically improved properties. In particular, several nanofillers has shown to produce a significant improvement of the combustion behavior in the polymer matrix which they are embedded in, both thermoplastics and thermosets. In the project, a PFA nanocomposite filled with silica nanoparticles was developed and its thermal and combustion behavior studied (1). The nanocomposite mixture was obtained with the support of a commercial water-based colloidal suspension that was mechanically mixed with the PFA prepolymer.

The used raw PFA system together with the use of liquid suspension of the filler lead to a processing that can be easily up-scaled. The silica source selected in this work was a Ludox™ type commercial colloidal silica. The use of specific functional silanes (amino, isocyanate) to modify the surface the silica was found paramount to get an even distribution of colloidal silica particles in a cured PFA matrix.

Figure 3: scanning electron microscopy of fracture surfaces.

Left: colloidal silica (8wt%) modified PFA matrix without surface modification leading to agglomeration of silica domains.

Right: colloidal silica (8wt%) modified PFA matrix with aminosilane surface modification showing homogenous dispersion of nanoparticles in the cured PFA .

The presence of dispersed colloidal silica into the cured matrix also has a profound effect on further improvement on the decrease in combustion rate at elevated temperatures (Figure 4). Whereas a cured PFA already possess a good thermal stability this can be further optimized at high temperatures using colloidal silica nanoparticles.

Figure 4: TGA and DTG curves in air of neat cured PFA matrix surface and PFA matrix modified with functionalised colloidal silica.

c) Application of PFA resins in case study demonstrators for public transport.

Using RTM and wet lay up manufacturing PFA-glass fibre reinforced composites were tested according mass transportation fire standards for Rail applications (EN 45545-2:2013,) reaching HL3 classification.

The demonstrator for Marine applications was an innovative bulkhead sandwich construction made from PFA/glass laminates and a triple cork core solution to cope a load also under a severe fire.

The bulkhead construction was tested in a large scale IMO fire test without any mineral wool insulation on the fire side, which is the standard solution for a bulkhead of steel, but had a thin coating of intumescent paint for extra protection. The test was a success as the bulkhead passed all test criteria well below the 60-minute limit (2).

Figure 5: triple core PFA/glass sandwich material in large scale IMO fire test

SUMMARY:

Within the FireResist project it was proven that renewable Polyfurfuryl alcohol (PFA) can be used as matrix for fire resistant composites. A number of manufacturing techniques including prepreg or liquid moulding were used to make glass fibre reinforced composites with exceptional resistance to fire comparable to standard phenolic resins.

Further modifications to the cured PFA matrix can be performed by the use colloidal silica nanoparticles which have received an additional surface treatment. This hybrid organic-inorganic PFA system shows an improved resistance to combustion at temperatures above 400°C.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS:

The research leading to these results received funding from the European Community's Seventh Framework Programme (FP7/2007-2013) under Grant Agreement No. 246037 (Project Fire-Resist).

<http://www.fire-resist.eu/>

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